

Rural Settlement Pattern in Nanded District: A Geographical Review

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Abstract

Such studies are necessary for determining various aspects and problems associated with the human beings. Settlement geography is recent branch of human geography. Settlement is an establishment way of life, an abode, a shelter or dwelling where man retires from his days work for relief. The study of habitat is relatively recent sprout from the venerable trunk of human geography. 'Settlement' term is derived from the word settle. The word 'settle' means to establish or become established in more or less permanent abode. It also means temporary residence at a place. Settlement is the basic need of human being. Settlement is divided into two parts that is urban and rural settlement.

Key words settlement, establish, place, human being, rural settlement

Introduction

During human adaptation with the environment, man came in close contact to various environmental features and this adaptation brought fourth change in his physical landscape. These changes are identified as cultural landscape and present man's relation to man upon earth. 'Settlement' means the settlement units representing an organized colony of human beings together with the buildings in which they live or that they otherwise use and the paths and streets over which they travel. Settlement is concerned not only with buildings grouped around the permanent farm dwelling, but also with the temporary camp of the hunter or herder, or with settlement clusters or

agglomeration, running the scale from hamlet to village, to town, to city and to metropolis.

A definition incorporating both the themes in best possible way is that "rural settlement geography is concerned with the orderly description and interpretation of processes, patterning, functions and the spatial organization of human occupance within rural environment over the earth surface.

Study Area

Nanded district is located in the eastern part of Marathawada. It lies in Godawari river basin. It extends from 18° 16' north latitude to 19° 55' north latitude and 76° 56' east longitude to 78° 19' East longitude. It covers an area of 10527.87 KM² and has a population of 3361292 as per the 2011 census.

This district is divided into 16 tahsils for administration. These are Nanded, Ardhapur, Mudkhed, Mahoor, Kinwat, Hadgaon,

Himayatnagar, Bhokar, Umri, Biloli, Naigaon, Dharmabad, Kandhar, Loha, Mukhed and Deglur

Research Methodology

The present study has been accomplished with the help of scientific methods both in the field and in the laboratory. Following statistical techniques are used to understand the pattern of settlement

1. Dispersal Index : $\frac{\text{Average Population Size of Settlements}}{\text{Average Spacing of Settlements}}$
- a. Average Population Size of Settlements : $\frac{\text{Total Rural Population}}{\text{Number of Settlements}}$
- b. Average spacing : $\sqrt{\frac{\text{Total Rural Area}}{\text{Number of Settlements}}}$

Settlement Classification

A rural settlement is mainly an agricultural workshop and as such it cannot be separated from the land whose use it ensures. Its shape and arrangements are often in strict accord with the kind of work, the agricultural technique and the way the soil is used. According to Arousseau the arrangement of rural settlements as geographical entities express the grouping of dwellings and their inter-relationship, makes the different types of rural settlements.

Rural settlements are classified in different ways. Some geographers have considered site as important criteria for the classification of rural settlements. On the one hand the pattern has been guided by physical aspects such as nature of topography, source of water supply, drainage

pattern, soil condition, etc. On the other hand it is also related to the socio-economic conditions such as land use, land tenure, crop association, means of transportation and density of population.

Many geographers have studied settlement types but they have not given their clear explanation. Demangeon tried to explain why rural settlements are dispersed or agglomerated. According to him, villages are compact in plain areas whereas in rugged or broken area dispersed settlements are more common.

Settlement Types

For purpose of classification a statistical method of Mandal has been applied and the results have been presented through a table and a map. Considering size and spacing of rural settlements dispersal index is calculated as follows:

Spacing, Size And Dispersal Index

Sr. No.	Tahsil	Average Spacing	Average Population Size	Dispersal Index
	Nanded	2.18	1889	866.5
	Mudkhed	2.49	1540	618.4
	Ardhapur	2.35	1863	792.7
	Bhokar	2.71	1471	542.8
	Umri	2.50	1154	461.6
	Kandhar	2.53	1536	607.1
	Loha	2.57	1521	591.8
	Deglur	2.88	1439	499.6
	Mukhed	2.45	1437	586.5
	Biloli	2.62	1554	593.1
	Dharmabad	2.45	1084	442.4
	Nigaon	2.57	1873	728.7
	Kinwat	2.86	1020	356.6
	Mahoor	2.43	975	401.2
	Hadgaon	2.67	1358	508.6
	Himayatnagar	3.05	1288	422.2
	District	2.58	1437.6	563.7

Source : Compiled by the Author

Settlement Formation:

Values of Dispersal index have been grouped according to median and quartile values. The higher values indicate compact settlements whereas, lower values indicate sprinkled settlements. The dispersal values range from 356.6

to 866.5 The spatial distribution of settlements according to types is as follows :

c. Compact Settlement:

The table clearly shows that the compact settlements are found in fertile tracts of the Godavari and Manyad rivers. This includes

Nanded, Mudkhed, Ardhapur and Nigaon tahsils. Rainfall and irrigation are important factor affecting settlements types. In areas of poor rainfall in Balaghat and Mudkhed ranges, surface water accumulates in ponds therefore; compact settlements are built around these water-bodies. In areas where the ponds are frequent & deep wells and tube wells are constructed, the settlements are compact e.g. Betak Biloli, Sugaon, Pvedwadi, Punegaon, etc.

In this group of tahsils the average size of the rural settlements is comparatively large. And most of the settlements located in these tahsils have dense population and close spacing between the houses. This is the area where agriculture is highly developed. The dispersal values in this group range from 607.2 to 866.5.

d. Semi Compact Settlement :

The semi compact settlement is an intermediate type between the zones of compact and sprinkled settlements and is more common in the extensive fertile areas where the water table is high and wells can be sunk, easily. Such type of settlements is found in areas where the drainage texture is dense particularly in Loha, Kandhar and Mukhed tahsils. Wadi inhabited by low caste people surrounding the main settlement is a peculiarity of this type. The range of dispersal values of this group is from 564.3 to 607.1.

e. Semi sprinkled settlement:

Semi sprinkled settlements are found in the areas characterized by adverse physical conditions as rugged topography with low rainfall. A Wadi inhabited by workers and low caste people surrounding the main settlement is a peculiarity of this types e.g. settlements in Hadgaon, Bhokar, Umri and Deglur tahsils. These settlements are small in size and they are located near cultivable land. The dispersal values range from 442.5 to 564.21 for this group.

f. Sprinkled Settlement:

Sprinkled settlements are scattered in the areas of forest and hilly areas with drier climate and poor soils. Houses are largely made of materials gathered from forest e.g. settlements in Kinwat and Mahoor tahsil. Sprinkled settlements are also found in Himayatnagar and Dharmabad tahsils. The average population size in these tahsils is less than 1300. Most of the hamlet or wadi forms of rural settlement are dominant in these tahsils. The dispersal values of this group range from 442.4 to 356.6.

Conclusion

Dispersal index is calculated to analyze the types of rural habitats considering population size and average spacing of rural habitats in the region. This study reveals that compact settlements are more in

fertile areas of the Godavari and Manyad river basin and sprinkled and semi-sprinkled settlements are more in hilly and forested areas of Kinwat and Bhokar tahsil.

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